

EXAMINING THE LEVELS OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS DOING SPORTS – THE CASE OF BURDUR, TURKEY

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the Academic Motivation levels of students participating in secondary school sports activities by considering some variables. In this study, the Academic Motivation Scale developed by Bozanoğlu in 2004 was applied to 200 students from different secondary schools located in the city center of Burdur. At the end of the study, it was observed that the level of academic motivation of secondary school students who did sports had significant difference in terms of age, gender, class and vocational high school. In addition, there was no significant difference between doing licensed sports and sports branches. The results of the analyses showed that male students who did sports had higher levels of academic motivation than girls. The obtained data were supported by various sources in the literature. Although it is confirmed in the analysis results that doing sports has effects on academic motivation levels, it needs to be investigated in terms of other factors affecting the level of academic motivation.

Keywords: motivation, secondary school students, school sports

1. Introduction

With the study “Examining the Levels of Academic Motivation of Secondary School Students Doing Sports - The Case of Burdur, Turkey”, it was aimed to investigate the academic motivation levels of secondary school students who did sports.

The sporting event creates a general unity of athletes, teachers, coaches, experts, managers, senior management, state sports organizations, audiences and sports press. If there is a break and inadequacy in those items that are linked to each other, others will

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be affected negatively by this. If young people are educated in line with the core of sports, and if the teacher, coach, school manager bring conditions like success, announcing the name of the team, the school, the region, to develop his reputation or to meet his personal concerns before the individual, these will kill sporting virtues and sports.

Sportive Education must be widespread among young people and within the society. Sports Training is a right for people. When this right is distributed evenly, it is possible to speak of a Sportive Virtue in any institution, organization and person that are both inside and outside the scope of being an athlete involved in sportive events (Erdemli, 1996). These advantages or disadvantages may play roles in developing positive or negative attitudes towards Physical Education classes in schools by students who are actively involved in sports or by students who are not involved in any sportive activity. The sport which is professionally done in full day and the one done in leisure times constitutes two sides of sports that are mostly favored. These factors are the ones that will make children in the educational period become aware of sports and direct them to sports. Family, media, school, teacher, official institutions responsible for sports and sports clubs are the main elements in the orientation of young people (Karaküçük, 1997).

Education does not end at the end of formal education; it lasts for a whole lifetime. Education involves the whole life of the individual. Lifelong learning involves organized, widespread and routine learning carried out in all areas of an individual's life, in order to ensure the greatest development in the individual's private life, family, and in social and professional life. Thus, lifelong education involves and integrates the stages and forms of education, i.e. pre-school, primary, secondary and higher education, organized, widespread and normal education (DPT, 2001).

Man should be evaluated as a whole with physical, mental and spiritual aspects; and education should be organized in such a way to realize these services. With Physical Education activities, the individual learns to recognize his own abilities and other abilities, to compete in equal conditions, to appreciate others by admitting defeat, to be modest when winning, and to learn to use his/her time and effort in the most appropriate way. In this sense, Physical Education is an important tool of contemporary education system which aims to prepare the individual for life. In order to reach this aim, Physical Education activities should be sufficient at every level of education starting from pre-school education (Mirzeoğlu, 2003). The main aim of Physical Education and sport, which has a big importance in general education, is to help students to reach the highest level of movement capacity by educating them with physical activities (Çöndü, 2004). Physical Education also contributes to bring the physical, mental, social and emotional development of children to the highest level in terms of physical, mental, social and emotional development. Physical Education in this framework, is an active lifestyle involving physical continuum, to participate in physical activity, and to ensure student development, knowledge, attitudes, motor and behavioral skills in school Physical Education programs (Kangalgil, Hünük, Demirhan, 2006). For students who are actively involved in sports and for those who are not, these

advantages or disadvantages may play roles to develop positive or negative attitudes towards Physical Education classes in schools. As in other areas, students in the school environment also develop attitudes towards physical education and sports lessons. Positive attitudes of the students in Physical Education classes can also stimulate the teacher in providing efficient processing of the course (Kangalgil, Hünük and Demirhan, 2006). In order to sustain the life of the individual in a balanced way, the society in which s/he lives must be equipped with constructive behavior patterns. The tool that will provide this is education (Hizal, 1982). The common aspect that emerges from these definitions is that education is a kind of behavior modification, behavior creation and planned activities. The main function of education is to give individuals the characteristics desired by the society. This function is intended to be given to the students through the teaching-learning activities organized in the educational institutions within the education system (Özer, 1993).

Education does not consist of mere experiences that are made and achieved on specific days and hours in schools. Education, in general, includes ongoing changes and practices in and out of school. Permanent or temporary changes in the behavior of individuals due to their own movements shape the mental, physical, emotional and moral aspects of human life (Karaküçük, 1999). In its simplest definition, education is the process of changing behaviors. The realization of this process depends only on how the individual learns by doing, living and practicing. In addition, there is a need for short and long-term planning to prevent undesirable developments in the behavior of the individual and to reveal desired behaviors. To repeat the definition of education; "It is the process of making desired changes in the behaviors of the individual through his/her own experiences". Education includes activities for a specific purpose. Because of this feature, it is carried out in schools, which are educational institutions. Schools attract attention as places where planned and regular education takes place in social life (Bilen, 2002).

An educational administrator has great responsibility when these aims are carried out; s/he applies the rules to all in an equal manner. S/he gives the remuneration of the individual's labor; and acts in a fair manner. S/he does not exploit the rights of others; and does not take sides in disputes between subordinates; strives to correct injustices. Makes the punishment in an equal manner to the committed crime; and allows individuals to exercise their legal rights. S/he acts objectively in evaluations; and avoids actions that harm people (Gültekin, 2008). According to Atesoglu (1974), sport is the fight that one carries out with himself/herself and a race usually with his/her competitors.

According to dictionaries, sports is all of the body movements applied in line with some rules, made in the form of individual or collective competitions. According to Büker's definition of sport in 1993, "It is an aesthetic, technical, physical, contestant, and social process of basic skills and fighting methods that people acquired when fighting the nature depending on the increase in free time for a peaceful form and to distract and move away from work for some time" (Bücher, 1993). The activities that develop socializing, integrating with society, developing spiritual and physical skills, promoting competence, solidarity

and cooperation with the public, improve skills and transform the natural environment into the human environment; they require being engaged in activities involving individual or collective leisure or collective activities under certain rules, with or without tools, which constitute cultural phenomena, and which are also called sports (Erkal, Güven and Ayan, 1998).

According to Erdemli (2002), sport is a participatory and racing-based activity guided by reason and by certain rules. It is targeted to the aim as well as being a fruitful activity in which the human organism participates physically, socially and intellectually. Sport is a social phenomenon, a culture. In addition, the aims of sports are to maintain health, develop personal skills and achieve success as individuals and groups in specific competitions. Therefore, it should be taken as a whole. Because human being is a bio-psycho-social integrity. It would be incomplete to examine the human being only with the body or spiritual side. The human being is also a social phenomenon and a special culture. The community members who have acquired the habit of doing Physical Education and sports for health have also created a productive society in addition to this principle. In addition, the international achievements in any kind of sports contribute to the development and proliferation of our cultural values while creating a common feeling and consensus (Yalçiner, 2003).

According to Erdemli (2006), individuals who start their sporting activities and who are generally at the lowest level of their sportive status, reach a new awareness and desire by seeing what level they are as a result of competitions. As people do sports, they start to live by knowing themselves. To know yourself, to be the best, to become competent is an undeniable fact for human beings to reach a high level in life. School sports are activity programs that are conducted in primary and secondary schools, universities and other institutions, designed and developed in accordance with the skills and abilities of all students to develop these skills and abilities. School sports are held with voluntary participation in competitions, physical fitness events, and outdoor events.

School sports offer opportunities for performing competitions and various physical activities to individuals at every skill level. These are in-school competitions and in-school and out-of-school sporting events. Sports club activities are included in and out of school and in competitions (Bucher, 1987).

For the individuals forming the society, to be healthy, agile and productive, to have balanced personality developments, in short; having physical, mental, emotional, and social skills are the most effective means of physical education and sport activities in the development and direction of physical education. Every human action must have creative, enhancing, and empowering aspects when it is performed. It is very important that the teacher who gives children the opportunity to meet sports is a sports educator since primary school years when s/he did sporting activities. In school sports, physical, intellectual and social consciousness is formed in children and young people. New values will be acquired in sports and social relations around this consciousness (Şahin, 2008).

In civilized societies, Physical Education classes are included in the curriculum as much as science, social sciences, arts and literature lessons. The importance of Physical Education, which started as a class in our schools many years ago, has not yet been recognized in terms of social, psychological and cultural consequences for a long time. We cannot claim that young people who are under the age of growth and sexual oppressions can solve their temporary depressions with Physical Education. Dismissing the Physical Education that will play an active role in acquiring personality of the young by eliminating the vibrations caused by the physiological changes will cause future difficulties that will be difficult to resolve. Physical Education has been inadequate in general education; and it is accelerating our people to move away from sports. The problem should be brought to the agenda frequently, because giving enough importance to Physical Education will change the understanding and value judgments in the society in a rapid manner. Physical Education program should be rearranged in the light of multi-faceted events since the interest in sports will start at school years and the benefits of it will be understood over time; and in addition, these programs should also consider the life after school (Kılıç, 2006).

“The most effective means in the development and direction of body, mind, emotions and social skills needed for healthy, agile, resourceful and productive, balanced personality development are Physical Education and sports activities.” (MoNE, Sports Competition Directive, 2006).

“It is necessary to make Physical Education and sports activities an indispensable habit in human life in order to reduce the depression and oppression that the developing technology, rapid urbanization and other life conditions bring to the individuals and to alleviate the adverse physical and moral effects on human beings, and thus, to create a healthy society. The most appropriate age for this habit is when students are in the primary and secondary education institutions.” (MoNE, Sports Competition Directive, 2006).

In order for learners to take an active part in the learning process, they must be willing to participate in this process, that is, they must be motivated. Students' reluctance to learn may lead to failure of the process, even though the goals are appropriate to the student's level, even though the techniques used in the learning-teaching process are appropriate. In other words, motivation is one of the most important factors affecting the learning-teaching process (Kelecioğlu, 1992). In many studies (Pintrich and Smith, 1993; Garcia and Pintrich, 1996; Zimmerman and Martinez-Pans, 1990; Pintrich and De Groot, 1990), it is emphasized that high motivation levels of students and high-level learning strategies affect academic success positively.

Fidan (1996) regards motivation as one of the most important power sources determining the direction and intensity of student behaviors in school. Motivation is defined as an internal condition that awakens, directs and sustains behavior (Woolfolk, 1998).

Motivation is the whole of one's behavior and expectations. Motivation includes behavior that occurs as a result of desires. A motivated person is someone who has integrated his knowledge and his beliefs with successful behavior. Motivation, although dependent on anticipation, also involves the perception of one's own competences and the control of effort (Stipek, 1998). Keller explained motivation as the direction of the effort and the inner force that motivated the student to learn (Keller, 2000, Warren, 2000).

The root of the concept of motivation is "*movere*" in Latin and it means "*to move*". However, in recent years, the concept of "*motivation*" has become more preferred among psychologists and educators (Bozanoğlu, 2004). Many psychologists and educators are consensual that student motivation is an important factor in school learning (Ryan and Connell, 1998). Academic motivation is an important concept which determines the strength of the insistence, effort, and the willpower of students in academic matters; and affects student achievement. Academic motivation can simply be defined as a factor that influences the attendance to school and to grades at school (Clark and Schroth, 2010).

2. Method

The questionnaire method was used in the study. As a model in the study, firstly, the effects on the academic motivation level of the secondary school students according to the demographic variables and the sporting situations were discussed; and then the data were collected and evaluated on the effects of doing and not doing sports actively on academic motivation.

The universe of the study consisted of 2764 middle school students studying at the secondary education institutions in Burdur city center. The sampling of the study consisted of 200 students studying at 9, 10, 11 and 12th grades at Burdur Sports High School, Burdur USO Anatolian High School, Burdur Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School, Çayboyu Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School, Ercan Akın Science High School, Burdur Mehmet Uzal Social High School, and were selected by Random Sampling Method. A total of 200 students which consisted of 81 female students (40.5%) and 119 (59.5%) male students participated in the present study.

As a method of collecting data in the survey, a questionnaire was used whose validity and reliability in the literature were tested in previous studies. The Academic Motivation Scale used in the study was developed by Bozanoğlu in 2004; and consists of 20 statements. The personal information form and the scale were applied to the schools after permission was received. A total of 230 questionnaires were distributed, of which 30 were found to have missing data or were incomplete. These forms were not included in the study results. A questionnaire consisting of 6 questions was used as a personal information form in the study. In the questionnaire used, there were 6 questions aiming to determine information about the demographic characteristics of the students.

3. Findings

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distributions of the Personal Information of the Participants

Variables	Sub-Variables	f	%
Gender	Female	81	40,5
	Male	119	59,5
Age groups	15 years of age	51	25,5
	16 years of age	56	28,0
	17 years of age	54	27,0
	17+ years of age	39	19,5
Grade levels	9 th Grade	63	31,5
	10 th Grade	56	28,0
	11 th Grade	39	19,5
	12 th Grade	42	21,0
Doing sports with license status	Yes	161	80,5
	No	39	19,5
Sports branch type	Football	32	16,0
	Volleyball	90	45,0
	Basketball	10	5,0
	Handball	10	5,0
	Table tennis	6	3,0
	Judo	3	1,5
	Wrestling	7	3,5
	Athletics	6	3,0
	Other	36	18,0
School type	Sports High School	24	12,0
	Anatolian and Equal High School and Equal High S.	45	22,5
	Vocational High School	66	33,0
	Social Sciences High School	28	14,0
	Science High School	37	18,5
	Sports High School	24	12,0

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that 81 women (40,5%) and 119 men (59,5%) participated in the study according to gender variable. When the age groups are examined, it is seen that 56 people are in the group of 16 years of age constitute 28.0%. In addition, 54 students in the age group of 17 constitute 27%. According to the class level, the 9th Grade constitute 31.5% with 63 students, while the 11th Grade constitutes 19,5% with 39% students. 161 students who do licensed sports constitute 80.5% while those who did not do sports constitute 39 people with 19.5%. According to sports branch types, 90 people who prefer volleyball branch constitute 45% while 3 people who prefer judo sport constitute 1.5%. When the school types are examined, it is seen that 66 people prefer sports high school at maximum level with 33% and 24 people prefer sports high school at minimum level with 12%.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants

N	Minimum	Maximum	X	Sd
200	24	96	72,10	12,837

When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that the academic levels of the participants are above the medium level.

Table 3: Comparison of Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants according to Gender

Gender	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave.	Rank Tot.	U	p
Female	81	69,43	13,692	88,91	7201,5	3880,5	,019
Male	119	73,91	11,942	108,39	12898,5		

When Table 3 is examined it is seen that there are differences between the academic motivation levels of the participants according to their genders at a statistically significant level ($p < 0,05$), and that male participants have higher academic motivation levels when compared with female participants.

Table 4: Comparison of Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants according to Age Groups

Age Groups	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave	x2	p	Differences between Groups
15 years of age	51	69,84	12,237	88,62	9,704	,021	1-4, 2-4
16 years of age	56	70,36	14,291	91,86			
17 years of age	54	72,30	13,093	104,19			
17+ years of age	39	77,26	9,621	123,35			

When Table 4 is examined it is seen that there are differences at a statistically significant level between the academic motivation levels of the participants according to the age groups ($p < 0,05$). This difference stems from the fact that the academic motivation levels of the participants at the age of 17+ are higher than the participants at the 15 and 16 age groups.

Table 5: Comparison of Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants According to Grade Levels

Grade Levels	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave.	x2	p	Difference between Groups
9 th Grade	63	72,40	12,378	100,77	21,316	,000	1-2, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4
10 th Grade	56	66,34	14,078	75,04			
11 th Grade	39	73,10	11,459	106,08			
12 th Grade	42	78,38	9,680	128,87			

When Table 5 is examined it is seen that there are differences between the academic motivation levels of the participants at a statistically significant level ($p < 0,05$). The academic motivation levels of the 56 participants who were studying at the 10th Grade is seen to be 75,04.

Table 6: Comparison of the Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants According to Licensed Sporting Status

Licensed Sporting Status	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave.	Rank Tot.	U	p
Yes	161	72,14	12,538	101,01	16263,0	3057,0	,799
No	39	71,92	14,176	98,38	3837,0		

When Table 6 is examined it is seen that the academic motivation levels of the participants do not differ according to doing licensed sports status at a statistically significant level ($p < 0,05$). While 161 participants said “Yes” (80.5%), 39 participants said “No” (19,5%).

Table 7: The Comparison of Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants according to Sports Branches

Branch Type	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave.	x2	p
Football	32	74,63	13,067	113,81		
Volleyball	90	71,54	13,203	97,96		
Basketball	10	74,30	13,242	107,25		
Handball	10	67,60	7,183	74,95		
Table tennis	6	74,17	4,491	109,83	11,280	,186
Judo	3	88,67	4,933	179,50		
Wrestling	7	75,29	5,908	114,71		
Athletics	6	71,50	10,932	90,17		
Other	36	69,61	14,498	91,06		

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that the academic motivation levels of the participants do not differ at a statistically significant level according to sports branches ($p < 0,05$). While 19 participants preferred volleyball at the highest level with 45%, 3 participants preferred Judo at the lowest level with 1,5%.

Table 8: Comparison of the Academic Motivation Levels of the Participants according to School Types They Study at

School Type	N	X	Sd	Rank Ave.	x2	p	Differences between Groups
Sports High School	24	73,88	13,469	108,92			
Anatolian and Equivalent High Schools	45	68,78	12,940	84,30			
Vocational High School	66	76,27	10,945	118,73	13,114	,011	2-3, 3-5
Social Science High School	28	70,11	15,110	95,46			
Science High School	37	69,03	11,922	86,04			

When Table 8 is examined, it is seen that there are differences between the academic motivation levels of the participants according to the school type they study at. The participants who preferred vocational high schools were 66 participants with 33%, and the participants who preferred Sports High Schools at the lowest level were 24 participants with 12%.

4. Results

At the end of the research, it was observed that the level of academic motivation of secondary school students was significantly different when examined in terms of age, gender, class and Vocational High School. There was a statistically significant difference

between the levels of academic motivation according to gender of the participants ($p < 0,05$), and the academic motivation levels of the male participants were higher than female participants. According to gender, 81 women constituted 40,5% while 119 men constituted 59,5%.

There was a statistically significant difference between the academic motivation levels of the participants according to age groups ($p < 0,05$). This difference stems from the fact that the motivation levels of the participants in the 17+ age group are higher than those in the 15 and 16 age group.

There was a statistically significant difference between the academic motivation levels of the participants according to their grade levels ($p < 0,05$). The motivation level of 56 participants who are studying in the 10th class is seen as 75.04.

The level of academic motivation of participants do not differ statistically according to licensed sports situations ($p < 0,05$). While 161 participants said “yes” (80.5%), 39 participants said “No” (19.5%).

The level of academic motivation does not differ statistically according to the sports branches of the participants ($p < 0,05$). While 90 people who preferred volleyball as the sports branch were 45%, 3 people who preferred Judo branch were 1.5%.

It is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the levels of academic motivation according to the types of schools in which the participants are educated. According to the school type, 66 people who preferred the highest occupation were 33%, while 24 people who preferred the least sports were 12%.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference between the high schools in terms of doing licensed sports and sports branches. It is seen in the analyses results that the male students who perform sports have higher academic motivation levels than girls. When the age of the participants is considered, it is seen that the most motivated students are at the age of 17 and above, while at the class level, the motivation of the students in the 12th grade is high depending on their age. It was observed that the level of academic motivation of Vocational High School students was higher than that of Anatolian and Science High students in high school types. In general terms, the academic motivation levels of the participants were above the moderate level. The obtained data were supported by various sources in the literature. Although it is confirmed in the analysis results that sporting has an effect on academic motivation level, it needs to be investigated in terms of other factors affecting the level of academic motivation. Based on the results of the research, the following suggestions can be made;

1. Investigation of various variables related to the cognitive field during the year by choosing the students who do and do not do sports activities in different school types during the period of education and training in order to see the effect of secondary sports students' academic motivation levels on their participation levels (participation in classes, classes loved and not loved, grades, behaviors, viewpoints about the future) to obtain clearer results.
2. The number and quality of physical areas can be increased in order for secondary school students to be able to play sports in schools, and more students should be

withdrawn into sports and the durations of the physical education lessons and sports in schools must be prolonged.

3. Parents, school administrations, teachers and secondary school students should be informed about sports and they must be told that sports not only have physical benefits but also have a strong influence on the level of academic motivation.
4. Physical education curriculums in schools should be more functional in order for sports culture be established and proper sports consciousness be acquired by students.

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